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**Yield stability and performances in conventional and conservation agriculture on durum wheat in Sardinia.
Report related to WP 2**

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1. Abstract

Conservation agriculture (CA) is a sustainable farming practice aimed at enhancing environmental resilience while maintaining crop productivity. In the Mediterranean area, where agricultural systems are increasingly affected by soil degradation, water scarcity, and climate variability, CA offers a potential solution. This study evaluates the effects of CA and conventional systems on the grain yield and yield stability of durum wheat in a long term experiment (LTE) conducted in southern Sardinia (Italy). In this study over 11 cropping seasons (2004/05–2014/15) of field trials, conducted in two experimental sites, were considered. The experiment was organized in a randomized split plot design with three replications to compare three tillage systems (conventional, reduced, and sod seeding) and two crop rotations (continuous wheat and legume-wheat rotation).

In order to analyze the complex interactions between environment and crop managements applied in the LTE, several multivariate analysis techniques were applied.

Results showed that crop management involving legume-wheat rotations produced higher grain yields on durum wheat, while tillage had no significant effect under rotational systems. In contrast, continuous wheat cultivation with conventional tillage produced the lowest grain yields that were also less stable.

PLS regression revealed that the main environmental indicator for grain yield is rainfall patterns. Rainfall after heading was crucial for grain yields with conventional tillage, while rainfall before heading are more important for conservation tillage management and especially for sod seeding which helps conserve soil moisture.

In conclusion, CA, particularly in rotation with legumes, enhances durum wheat yields and yield stability in the Mediterranean area. While conventional tillage under monoculture is being phased out, CA techniques offer a more resilient approach to managing limited water resources and ensuring stable crop productions.

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2. Introduction

Conservation agriculture (CA) is as a sustainable farming practice that aims to enhance environmental sustainability while maintaining or improving crop productivity. In the Mediterranean region, where agricultural systems are heavily impacted by increasing environmental pressures such as soil degradation, water scarcity, climate variability, exacerbated by climate change, CA offers a sustainable solution toward resilient and productive farming systems.

The staple crops of the Mediterranean area, such as durum wheat and legumes, are in general well adapted to the normal climate, but being rainfed crops they are at risk of suffering significant negative impacts from ongoing climate change. This is even more important for durum wheat which is one of the main crops being used for the most important food productions such as pasta, bread and cous cous.

CA is based on three main principles: minimal soil disturbance, crop rotations and permanent soil cover by cover crops or crop residues. This principles named also pillars of CA aim to optimize the use of resources while maintaining agricultural productivity and enhancing ecosystem services. By reducing soil disturbance CA can improve soil structure and reduce erosion. At the same time crop rotation, especially with leguminous crops, can enhance soil fertility (by fixing nitrogen with rhizobia) and reduce pest and disease of wheat by interrupting pathogen cycles. Conservation agriculture is considered also a typical example of climate smart agriculture that aims to increase productivity, enhance resilience, reduces greenhouse gas emission and enhances achievement of food security (FAO 2013).

The objective of this report is to study and evaluate the effect of conservation agriculture and conventional systems on both grain yield and yield stability of durum wheat over the long term. The LTE data were also used to identify the main environmental indicators that drive durum wheat yield and stability.

3. Methodology

Since 2003, a long term experiment (LTE) were conducted in the “S. Michele” experimental station of the Agris Sardegna, the Agricultural Research Agency of Sardinia (Italy). This LTE is located in southern Sardinia (39°25'29'' N, 09°04'55'' E, 99 m above sea level), on two different sites, Benatzu and Ussana, that are distant about 1 km from each other but the soil types are quite different (fig. 1)

- Benatzu: Inceptisol with vertic characteristics (Vertic Epiaquept) according to the U.S.D.A. soil taxonomy classification (Soil Survey Staff, 1999) with good fertility for cereal growing;

- Ussana: Alfisol (Petrocalcic Palexeralf) according to the U.S.D.A. soil taxonomy classification with ordinary fertility for cereal growing.

Figure 1 – LTE sites: Benatzu (up) and Ussana (bottom) and soli profiles of Benatzu (left) and Ussana (right).

3.1. Soil chemical characteristics

A summary of the main physical and chemical soil characteristics in the first 30 cm of depth are reported in table 1 for each site.

Table 1 – Main soil characteristics

Characteristic	Ussana	Benatzu
Texture	Sandy Clay Loam	Loam
sand (%)	55.8	44.0
silt (%)	18.2	30.1
clay (%)	26.0	25.9
pH in water	7.8	8.4
Organic Matter (%)	1.3	2.1
Total Nitrogen (‰)	0.8	1.0
P (Olsen) (ppm)	20.8	16.2
K (NH₄Ac) (ppm)	140	159
Na exch. (ppm)	43.3	23.1
C.E.C. (me/100g)	15.9	18.5
E.S.P. (%)	1.2	0.5

3.2. Climate

The climate in Sardinia is Mediterranean, characterized by hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters. Rainfall is highly seasonal, with most precipitations occurring during the winter months, with extended periods of drought in late spring and summer. The weather conditions in the two sites

are similar during the cropping season, as the sites are close each other, and the conditions are shown in figure 2. The cumulative rainfall in the October-June period is 417 mm, the minimum and maximum temperatures are 8.9 °C and 20.4 °C, respectively.

These climate conditions can be considered as representative of the cereal growing areas of Southern Italy.

Figure 2 – Thermo-pluviometric characteristics of Ussana

3.3. Experimental design and field trials management

The LTE started in 2003, was designed as a randomized complete block with a split-plot arrangement and three blocks. In the main plots, each one with an area of 2400 m², three types of tillage systems were applied: conventional tillage (CT), reduced or minimum tillage (RT) and no tillage or sod seeding (NT). In subplots, each one with an area of 600 m², two different crop rotations were applied: continuous wheat (WW) and legumes-wheat crops (LW) consisting in faba bean or field pea. Each rotation was duplicated to obtain data for all crops on a yearly basis. Hence, data coming from the WW are twice than those obtained with LW. In figures 3 the map of the experimental design is shown.

In this report we analyse the LTE conducted across 11 cropping seasons: from 2004/05 to 2014/15. The analysis focuses on this dataset because it allows the analysis of both the effect of tillage techniques and crop rotation. Indeed from 2015 changes in rotation treatments due to phytopathology problems caused by accumulation of nematodes (Foxi et al, 2017) especially with Continuous Wheat and Conventional Tillage.

Figure 3 - LTE Ussana 2007/08: map of the experimental design

The first year, 2003/04, necessary to achieve a right plot arrangement concerning the rotation treatments in each plot was not considered in these analyses.

3.4. Overview on the analyses performed.

The choice of the best yield stability indices for crop management in long-term experiments depends on various factors, including the specific objectives of the experiment and the environmental conditions. Over the years, numerous indices have been proposed, which, however, have their strengths and weaknesses. In addition to the well-known coefficient of variation (CV), numerous stability indices such as the Shukla's stability variance (1972) and Finlay and Wilkinson method (1963) have been widely used for many years especially for multi environmental trials (METs). It is very important to take into consideration that very often the treatments (more frequently genotype) × environment interaction (GEI) in METs are statistically significant and the discordance of the treatment's response in each environment making difficult the overall interpretation of the data.

In order to address the difficult interpretation of data obtained in METs with significant GEI, the most effective and valid methods is the use of multivariate techniques. In particular, the AMMI-Based Stability Statistics (deriving from the Additive Main effects and Multiplicative Interaction (AMMI) model (Gauch, 2002)) and the GGE Biplot approach (Yan and Kang, 2003) or the Sites Regression (SREG) model (Crossa and Cornelius, 1997) are the most widely used in the last 20 years. After that to analyse relations between environmental covariates and grain yields a partial least square

(PLS) regression analysis were performed (Vargas et al., 1998; Vargas et al., 1999, Vargas et al., 2001).

Similarly to the GGEor SREG biplot, the results of the PLS can be graphically displayed as biplot. The PLS biplot is made the first two PLS components or factors (loadings and scores obtained by PLS) depicted by vectors (or labels) with a starting points at the origin (0, 0) that ends on the value of the coordinates that represent environments, crop managements and environmental covariates. Crop managements and environments with the same directions have positive correlations; those having opposite directions have negative correlations. The PLS approach is particular interesting and efficient when the number of environmental covariates are numerous and exceeds that of the environments (Piepho and Blancon, 2023).

All statistical analyses were made by using R software: for the mixed models *lme4*, *lmerTest* and *emmeans* R packages. The GGEbiplot analysis was performed by using the *metan* package and PLS with the *PLS* package.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Performance and yield stability indices

A first analysis of yield stability has been performed by using the coefficient of variation as an inverse measure of yield stability. The figures 4-6 show the CVs for each treatment combination in Benatzu (fig. 4), Ussana (fig. 5) and together (fig. 6) year by year. However, these figures that represent the CVs distribution does not allow to understand what crop management permits obtaining more stable yields. Moreover it seems that yield stability depends on the year and site.

The identification of the best crop management for yield stability is not evident even when combining the data of the two sites (fig. 6).

For this reason, a more complex analysis considering both productivity and yield stability was performed by using mixed models of the METs site by site together. In the mixed model analyses performed, we considered years and replication (block) as random factors whereas the other factors (sites, tillage, rotation) were considered as fixed.

Fig. 1 – Distribution of CV for each crop management, year by year, at Benatzu site.

Fig. 2 – Distribution of CV for each crop management, year by year, at Ussana site.

Fig. 3 – Distribution of CV for each crop management, year by year both at Ussana and Benatzu.

As the GEI was statistically significant (data not shown), to interpret GEI the GGE biplot analysis was performed. The GGE biplot approach permits also to identify both the best crop

management for the productivity and, at the same time, to investigate for the more stable as already described by Yan and Kang (2003) .

Considering the main crop, which is durum wheat, the figure 7 reports both the more productive and stable crop management whereas in table 2 are reported the mean comparison between different crop managements in all environments. The best results for productivity were achieved with crop management that includes crop rotation between durum wheat and grain legumes (field beans or field peas) as can be observed in figure 7 and table 2.

Tillage	Rotation	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
Conventional Tillage	WL	3.34	a
Reduced tillage	WL	3.14	a
Sod seeding	WL	3.12	a
Conventional Tillage	WW	2.36	c
Reduced tillage	WW	2.51	b
Sod seeding	WW	2.57	b

Table 2 – Mean comparison between crop management

Fig. 4 – GGEbiplot of the LTE on conservation agriculture.

With the same rotation (WL), there are no significant differences between conservation (reduced tillage or sod seeding) and conventional tillage. Conservation tillage in monoculture caused significant lower yields than in rotation (Fig. 7 and Tab. 2). In monoculture, conservation tillage (reduced tillage and sod seeding) permits to obtain higher yields than conventional tillage. This last crop management (Conv till - WW) was the worst in term of productivity (Fig. 7 and Tab. 2).

It is important to take into account that the analysis of the average trend in productivity is only one aspect to be assessed for evaluating the best crop management since the productivity must be associated with the evaluation of the stability of crop production over the years.

Therefore, the best crop management must combine maximum productivity with good stability. As explained by Yan and Kang (2003) figure 7 provides also a graphical measurement of the yield stability: the further the treatments are graphically from the productivity axis (the green axis), the lower the yield stability.

According to the analyses carried out in this Sardinian LTE, conventional management associated with cereal monoculture should be avoided as this crop management is associated with the statistically worst yield values (on the left of fig. 7), and the lowest production stability (highest distance from the axis of stability) (fig. 7).

The analysis of yield stability was completed by calculating other alternative indices, although each has its strengths and weaknesses. The table 3 shows discordance between stability indices that are based on CV and more recent ones that are based on AMMI analysis and basically agree with the GGE method proposed in this report (table 3 and Fig 7-8).

4.2. Environmental indicators driving yield stability and performance.

For each environment, numerous environmental covariates were calculated. The covariates considered were the mean of minimum and maximum temperature and the cumulative precipitations and global solar radiation. These values were calculated both 30, 60, 90 and 120 days before (b) and 30, 60 and 90 days after heading. Indeed the heading phase of durum wheat is for durum wheat grain yield, especially in the Mediterranean area.

The results of the PLS regression analysis is resumed in the figure 9.

Table 3 - Other yield stability indices: numbers in bold indicate decreasing stability for the index considered

Treatments	means	CV	ACV	W		YSI	ASTAB	ASI	ASV	MASI	MASV	WAAS									
				Ecovalence																	
Conv till - WL	3.338	40.21	3	38.2	3	13.78	5	4	1	1.537	5	0.310	3	1.243	3	0.310	3	1.243	3	0.427	3
Conv till - WW	2.363	39.68	1	34.5	1	34.86	6	12	6	3.028	6	0.924	6	3.714	6	0.924	6	3.714	6	1.254	6
Red till - WL	3.139	40.21	2	36.4	2	7.84	2	4	2	0.285	2	0.194	2	0.781	2	0.194	2	0.781	2	0.345	2
Red till - WW	2.513	43.31	5	39.2	5	6.99	1	6	5	0.257	1	0.144	1	0.578	1	0.144	1	0.578	1	0.254	1
Sod seed - WL	3.117	41.23	4	39.1	4	8.24	3	8	3	0.498	3	0.365	5	1.467	5	0.365	5	1.467	5	0.526	4
Sod seed - WW	2.572	44.46	6	43.4	6	11.01	4	8	4	0.856	4	0.349	4	1.402	4	0.349	4	1.402	4	0.613	5

- CV** Coefficient of variance
- ACV** scale-adjusted coefficient of variation
- W**
- Ecovalence** Wricke's ecovalence
- YSI** Yield stability index
- ASTAB** AMMI Based Stability Parameter
- ASI** AMMI stability index
- ASV** AMMI stability value
- MASI** Modified AMMI stability index
- MASV** Modified AMMI stability value
- WAAS** Weighted Average of Absolute Scores for AMMI analysis

Fig. 8 – WAASY index (AMMI)

durum wheat grain yield, especially in the Mediterranean area. The results of the PLS is resumed in the figure 9.

Figure 9 – PLS biplot of loadings and scores for crop management (red), environments (blue) and environmental covariates (black): the covariate labels are composed by means an sums of covariates for specific period (number of days) and suffixes are "a" (after spiking) and "b" (before spiking)

The PLS biplot represented in figure 9 shows contemporarily environments (blue vectors), crop managements (red labels) and environmental covariates (black labels). The environments representing the early years of LTE are displayed on the left and the remaining on the right. Crop management labels are basically distributed along the second factor: sod seeding at the top of the biplot and conventional tillage at the bottom, according to a gradient of ‘soil disturbance’ that grows from the top to the bottom. The labels for reduced tillage are in an intermediate position, as the degree of disturbance is intermediate between sod seeding and conventional tillage.

The most important environmental covariates of this biplot are linked to precipitations (they are more distant from the origin and so the signal is stronger) that play important role for determining grain yield and act differently with crop management. Precipitations after heading is important

particularly for conventional tillage (same direction), whereas for sod seeding are more important the precipitations before heading. This result is not surprising especially in a Mediterranean environment where water is a limiting factor for crop growth in the late spring period (after heading). Under these conditions, with conservation tillage (especially for sod seeding) there is an higher soil water availability reducing yield stress compared to the fields (or plots) in conventional tillage. Indeed, it is well known that conservation tillage aims to conserve soil and water. Conversely, precipitation after heading are crucial for conventional tillage treatments that perform better respect conservation tillage in years with high precipitation amounts in spring.

Continuous wheat treatments tend to be on the left while those in rotation are on the right. This arrangement of treatments can be explained by a progressive reduction in yields due to an increasing nematode attack (Foxi et al. 2017) in the time and which led to the change in crop management by eliminating monoculture from the LTE in 2016.

5. Conclusions

Conservation agriculture provides reliable and stable durum wheat production in Mediterranean environments. Rotation with leguminous crops guarantees higher yields, while no differences were observed between different tillage treatments under rotation with leguminous crops. The worst crop management is conventional tillage with monoculture that determines low yields and reduced yield stability. Actually, this management is being progressively abandoned in the Mediterranean environment, especially after 2003 when it was discouraged by the mid-term review of the CAP. The results of the Sardinian LTE on conservation agriculture highlight that in the Mediterranean areas the most important limiting environmental factor affecting wheat production is rainfall. Conventional tillage is much more affected by spring rains than conservation tillage techniques, which have the advantage of conserving soil water more efficiently than conventional.

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